

RISK MANAGEMENT IN HOSPITAL MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Risk management is an extremely important point in the strategic analysis and planning of the hospital's activities.

Hospital organizations are exposed to a much wider range of adverse impacts than all other economic entities - companies, organizations, etc., because the content of the concept of risk in hospitals includes not only financial components, but also certain parameters of health.

Once the decision has been made that a certain risk needs to be managed, it can be done in several possible ways: elimination, minimization, transfer and acceptance.

Keywords: risk management, hospitals, strategic analysis, adverse impacts.

Introduction:

Risk management is an ancient idea. Ever since the time of the Old Testament, of ancient Rome, and of ancient China, there has been a desire among people both to predict future dangers and natural catastrophes, and to adapt to them.

It is accepted that the professor of insurance from Temple University (USA) Wayne Snider in 1955 first proposed the concept of "risk management". A year later, Russell Gallagher in Volume 34 of the Harvard Business Review first described the profession of risk manager.

In 1996, the Global Association of Risk Professionals (GARP) was also established, which is a non-governmental independent association of risk management practitioners and professionals. A risk manager is a specialist who has the knowledge and skills with the capabilities of a diverse set of tools to make or propose decisions on risk management in a particular organization.

Leading risk management organizations are the Risk and Insurance Management Society, Inc. (RIMS), founded in 1950, and the International Federation of Risk and Insurance Management (IFRIMA), formed in 1984. Apart from them, there are currently dozens of organizations that form a strong infrastructure of risk management. [2,3]

Risk management is an extremely important point of the strategic analysis and planning of the hospital's activity, including under conditions other than the understanding of "comfortable". [1]

The purpose of the article is to present significant aspects related to risk management in hospital medical institutions.

Exposure:

Risk management is a part of the activity of the management of an organization, which in a general sense is aimed at its effective protection (most often economic) from unwanted deliberate or accidental events, bringing certain primarily material damage to this organization. As a management activity, risk management requires the integrated efforts of the entire or-

ganization and includes decision-making and the realization (implementation) of the decisions made as a sequence of management impacts. This also defines the task of risk management as the process of selecting and implementing solutions that minimize a wide range of accidental or malicious events.

Each company, after adopting the general management strategy, also adopts a strategy for risks in general and for each specific risk in particular. In order to ensure the risk strategy, it is necessary to form a program for integrated risk management of the company. [2]

Risk management is a mechanism for managing risk exposure that allows us to recognize the events that may lead to adverse or harmful consequences in the future, the extent of their negative effect and how they can be controlled.

G. Komitov (2018) states the following working definition of risk management in hospital medical institutions:

"The identification, analysis, and control of risks that may threaten patient service, assets, or the image of the hospital organization."

Risk factors inevitably accompany the operation of the hospital in the modern conditions of a market economy and a strong competitive environment. *"The risk for the medical institution is a system of certain (risk) factors that simultaneously or successively in different periods of time exert their direct or indirect negative impact on the hospital's activity."* [1]

Hospital organizations are exposed to a much wider range of adverse impacts than all other economic entities - companies, organizations, etc., because within the content of the concept of risk in hospitals, not only financial components are included, but also certain parameters of health. While, for example, a commercial organization is exposed to the risk of low revenue, in the hospital treatment facility, the risk management problems are also related to the outcome of the hospital treatment - recovered, improved, unchanged or died. Ensuring better health also depends on the means that are provided for it, but the other more important condition is the implementation of an adequate and expedient

diagnostic-treatment process related to the professionalism of the hospital team, ensuring better health.

The most essential part of the control functions of managers at all management levels of the medical facility is their efforts to minimize substandard health services. According to the medical standards operating in our country, the hospital has extremely complex risk management and a complex toolkit for ensuring and managing the quality of the services it provides. The main reasons for this are: [4]

- the variety and serious nature of the diseases treated in the hospital;
- the complexity of the medical assistance provided;
- the intensity of the health services provided;
- absence, from a pragmatic point of view, of a difference in the significance of control over the quality of conditions (means), activities (processes) and results.

Structure of the management program for risk in the medical institution:

S. Spiridonov notes that support at all levels of the hospital's management structure is critical to the success of the risk management program. The importance of such support is also dictated by the fact that it is an integral part of the hospital's business plan and its strategic plans for development and activity. Providing the risk program with the necessary resources is evidence of support from the hospital's senior management. At the same time, it would be proper to plan and direct the control of the implementation of this program by a group appointed by the director of the hospital, which includes representatives of the Medical Council, the Council of Health Care, the Treatment Control Com-

mission and the Commission for the fight against nosocomial infections. This means that said program will have greater clinical effectiveness if risk management and quality assurance activities are integrated.

Hospital management should appoint a person to be responsible for risk management. It is necessary for this person to carry out the orders of the above-listed persons of the task force and report to them. Their duties should include activities on:

- detection and analysis of risks;
- creation and implementation of a resource-provided program approved by the hospital's management;
- reviewing all available and upcoming contracts with organizations for service of equipment, technical devices and installation facilities and controlling their implementation;
- supervision of all procedures related to the technical, fire, radiation and epidemiological safety of patients and staff;
- conducting staff training to improve their skills on the organizational aspects of risk management;
- personal participation in the elimination of losses personally incurred in unforeseen risk situations.

Table 1 shows the relationship between risk management and quality assurance activities:

It is important to note that complete overlap of risk management with quality assurance is not desirable due to the fact that the administrative orientation of the risk program and the clinical orientation of the quality assurance program require a number of activities and functions to address separately with different in nature control tools and management decisions.

Table 1.

Relationships between risk management and quality assurance activities

No	Risk management	Quality assurance
1	Protection of the material, technical and financial assets of the hospital	Related to the philosophy of the hospital
2	Protection of human and intangible values and resources	Improving the qualifications of all professionals
3	Preventing harm to patients, visitors, staff and property	Improving the quality of diagnostic, treatment and rehabilitation activities and care for the sick
4	Reducing total losses by targeting individual discrepancies and individuals	Comparing the quality of the provided health services with medical standards and measurable accreditation criteria
5	Loss prevention through: - accident prevention; - continuous ongoing observations on the quality of patient care (protocols and technical sheets for good general and specific nursing care); - control over compliance with the Charter of Patients' Rights	Prevention of future losses or - impairments of patients through continuous observations in problem areas (e.g. accreditation indicators marked as "mandatory")
6	Addressing any incident that occurs by applying the risk management steps: - risk identification; - risk analysis; - risk assessment; - processing of risk	Search for facts in the provision of health services that do not correspond to medical standards. Apply the following quality assurance steps: - identification of the problem; - determining the size of the problem; - implementation of corrective action; - continuation of relevant care and activities; - analysis of the obtained results

Source: Adapted from S. Spiridonov, 2012

Principles of hospital risk management:

The main steps of risk management consist of defining, evaluating, reducing, eliminating or transforming the risk.

Risk identification (recognition) can be done in many ways, but the most common of them is the collection and combination of data about different problems - a procedure that makes it possible to identify the risk area and make it the focus of action. There is a requirement that risk management efforts are not only rapid but at the same time focused on eliminating, reducing or restructuring risk.

The risk assessment should be carried out by reviewing and categorizing the information on the problems that are burdened with signs of risk (electrical network and outlets that include high pressure devices, septic operating rooms, etc.).

The elimination or reduction of risk can be achieved in the following ways:

- bringing the construction of the hospital building into compliance with safety standards;
- greater frequency in conducting internal audits on the implementation of medical standards for the quality of conditions (means), processes (activities) and results;
- improving relationships between patients and hospital staff;
- hiring external specialists to carry out specialized control of material areas and points, the exploitation of which may lead to the emergence of a risky situation.

The periodic evaluation of the efforts made by the staff to eliminate, reduce or transform the risk is also a prerequisite for a better implementation of the measures within the scope of risk management. [4]

CONCLUSION:

Risk management is carried out within the management of the hospital, as well as any other organization, and is an integral part of it.

The responsibility for implementing risk management within the organization rests with senior executive management.

Once the decision has been made that a certain risk must be managed, it can be done in several possible ways: elimination (liquidation), minimization (through certain steps to reduce its adverse effects to an acceptable level), transfer, i.e. exporting the identified risk to an external organization and acceptance – when there is nothing to be done in response to the impact of the risk factors.

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